

1 **OncoboxPD: human 51 672 molecular pathways database with tools for activity calculating**
2 **and visualization**

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25
26 **Abstract**

27 OncoboxPD (Oncobox pathway databank) available at <https://open.oncobox.com> is the collection of
28 51 672 uniformly processed human molecular pathways. Superposition of all pathways formed
29 interactome graph of protein-protein interactions and metabolic reactions containing 361 654
30 interactions and 64 095 molecular participants. Pathways are uniformly classified by biological
31 processes, and each pathway node is algorithmically functionally annotated by specific
32 activator/repressor role. This enables online calculation of statistically supported pathway activation
33 levels (PALs) with the built-in bioinformatic tool using custom RNA/protein expression profiles. Each
34 pathway can be visualized as static or dynamic graph, where vertices are molecules participating in a
35 pathway and edges are interactions or reactions between them. Differentially expressed nodes in a
36 pathway can be visualized in two-color mode with user-defined color scale. For every comparison,
37 OncoboxPD also generates a graph summarizing top up- and downregulated pathways.

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39 **Key words:** molecular pathway database, interactomics, protein-protein interactions, metabolomics,
40 pathway activation level, pathway visualization

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1. Introduction

Molecular pathway research is a rapidly growing field that is developing exponentially since the emergence of high-throughput microarray, next generation sequencing, proteomic technologies, and supporting bioinformatic tools [1–7]. Molecular pathways describe certain biological processes at the molecular level and include up to several hundred different molecular participants [7]. Molecular pathways most frequently are understood as networks of protein-protein interactions, or biochemical reactions, or their combinations [6].

At present, multitude of molecular interactions was documented, and thousands of molecular pathways were reconstructed and published [5,6]. The molecular interactions and reactions can be detected both experimentally and by using artificial intelligence methods [8,9].

Several high-throughput databases of molecular interactions and molecular pathways became available over the past decades, including Pathway interaction database [10], QIAGEN SABiosciences [11], Pathway Studio [12], Reactome [13], Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) [14], Signaling Pathways Integrated Knowledge Engine (SPIKE) [15], Metacyc [16], HumanCyc [17], and PathBank [6]. Some of these databases select pathways by their function, such as HumanCyc collection of human metabolic pathways[17], or SynSysNet collection of synaptic protein-protein interactions[18]. Some databases propose specific classification terms, e.g. *metabolism, genetic information processing, environmental information processing, cellular processes, organizational systems, diseases, drug development* categories of pathways in KEGG [14], or *metabolic, drug action, drug metabolism, disease, signaling, physiological* categories in Pathbank [6]. Alternatively, four molecular functions-based categories of *signaling, metabolic, cytoskeleton, and DNA repair* were recently proposed for the pathway classification [19].

However, to our knowledge all these pathway functional classification types are not algorithmically standardized, thus leading to non-uniformly functionally annotated groups of pathways. Importantly, pathways frequently describe complex molecular processes, and one pathway may be related to several functional categories. Furthermore, there is a lack of uniform annotation for the individual molecular participants of intracellular pathways (e.g. pathway nodes) in terms of their overall functional implication in the activation of a pathway.

With the increasing amount of OMICS data, new instruments are needed for the unbiased accurate high-throughput analysis of molecular pathways, including their annotation and visualization. At present there are several molecular pathway visualization tools [20] which can be grouped in two types. In the first type, the outputs are static pathway images not depending on the user's custom data. Such images are useful for illustrating functional interactions under study without integrating them with the molecular expression data [21]. In the second type tools, interactive figures can be obtained [22]. For example, KEGG software can use gene expression data to accentuate specific individual nodes on a pathway [14], and Reactome software can highlight relevant pathways on an overall interaction map [13]. PathBank software can process the input concentrations of metabolites while returning their adjusted visualization on an interactome graph [6].

However, next-generation molecular pathway analysis requires not only visualization, but also calculation of numeric pathway characteristics (e.g. extents of their up/downregulation) based on the user experimental data. Currently, there is a lack of uniformly assigned weights and coefficients reflecting each individual gene product/node role in the activation of a pathway under study.

Recently, an algorithmic approach was proposed for assigning of activation/repressor roles to the pathway components that was applied for the automatic annotation of 3040 pathways [23]. These roles were translated into node-specific numeric indexes necessary for calculating pathway activation levels (PALs).

92 Here, we present Oncobox pathway databank that accumulates 51 672 uniformly processed human
 93 molecular pathways extracted from different source databases. Superposition of all pathways formed
 94 interactome graph of protein-protein interactions and metabolic reactions containing 361 654
 95 interactions and 64 095 molecular participants. All pathways were functionally classified by their
 96 main underlying biological processes according to Gene Ontology (GO) tree. Each pathway node was
 97 algorithmically functionally annotated by specific activation/repressor role index. This enables direct
 98 calculation of pathway activation levels (PALs) using human RNA/protein expression profiles. With
 99 the Web-based bioinformatic tool or downloadable *oncoboxlib* Python library, user can analyze
 100 custom expression data to assess PALs in the samples of interest compared to the built-in or custom
 101 set of controls, and statistically evaluate differentially regulated pathways. Each pathway can be
 102 visualized both as static or dynamic graph, where vertices are molecules participating in a pathway
 103 and edges are interactions or reactions between them. Differentially expressed nodes in a pathway can
 104 be visualized in two-color mode with user-defined color scale. Online version of Oncobox PD is freely
 105 available at <https://open.oncobox.com>.

106 2. Materials and methods

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 108 OncoboxPD utilizes virtual machines (VMs) located in Microsoft Azure cloud. All VMs run on
 109 Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS. On the entry node, HTTP web server nginx is installed that is responsible for
 110 processing user requests (2 vCPUs, 8 GB RAM, D2s size according to Microsoft classification).
 111 HTTP server and the processes running in Python communicate through Web Server Gateway
 112 Interface (uWSGI 2.0.19 implementation).

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 114 JavaScript web application (running in the browser of a user) interacts via REST API with the
 115 backend. On the server we have a Python 3.7 application build on top of Django framework. A single
 116 instance of PostgreSQL 13.3 is used as a data storage.

117 Calculation tasks are sent via RabbitMQ queue for processing to compute optimized nodes (4-8
 118 vCPUs, 8-16 GB RAM, F4s-F8s size according to Microsoft classification). These settings can be
 119 dynamically scaled up or down depending on current workload. Once the calculation is complete, the
 120 results are returned to the main node and made available to the user.

121 3. Results

122 3.1. Database content

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 124 Oncobox pathway databank (OncoboxPD) includes 51 672 human molecular pathways extracted from
 125 seven pathway knowledge bases: Biocarta [24], KEGG [25], HumanCyc [17], Qiagen [11], NCI [10],
 126 Reactome [26] and PathBank [6]. The data were collected by combining manual and automatic parsing
 127 and curation of these source datasets. The processed pathways are stored in OncoboxPD with their
 128 original names in uniform format. Where possible, information on pathway participants and their
 129 interactions was extracted and catalogued (Table 1).

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 131 Table 1. Composition of source pathway knowledge bases

Source pathway knowledge base	Number of pathways*	Number of gene products*	Number of metabolites*	Type of interactions comprized
Biocarta 1.2	337	1 082	-	protein-protein
KEGG 1.2	288	4 345	-	protein-protein
HumanCyc 1.0	300	980	1 040	protein-protein, biochemical

				reactions, transport
NCI 1.2	775	2 214	-	protein-protein
Qiagen 1.4 (SABiosciences)	379	2 493	-	protein-protein
Reactome 1.3	945	6 105	-	protein-protein
Pathbank 1.0	48 648	1 405	55 571	protein-protein, biochemical reactions, transport
Total	51 672	9 117	56 596	protein-protein, biochemical reactions, transport

132 *Numbers are shown for unique items only

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134 Since most of the initial pathway formats had different nomenclatures for designation of genes,
135 proteins, metabolites, and others relevant items, in OncoboxPD we introduced uniform nomenclature
136 according to the following rules. All genes and their products are named according to HGNC
137 nomenclature [27], version from 17 July 2017; metabolites are annotated by full names and also linked
138 to IDs from Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) [28], Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI)
139 [29], The Human Metabolome Database (HMDB) [30], PathWiz [31] and DrugBank [32] resources,
140 where available.

141 In addition to full-size pathways, we also included so-called micropathways, where such
142 micropathway is a sub-graph of an existing pathway that contains major effector node and first to third
143 order neighbor nodes. The micropathways were generated automatically using our previously
144 published algorithm [23].

145 In the case of algorithmic parsing, the pathway connectivity data were controlled manually. The team
146 implementing expert curation could edit algorithmically assigned node or component names,
147 interaction marks and node composition to avoid artifacts, duplicates, and false interpretations.
148 Pathway size (number of participants in a pathway) varied substantially within and among original
149 datasets. In Biocarta, pathway size varied from 2 to 58 (average 16), in KEGG - from 1 to 284 (43),
150 in HumanCyc - from 4 to 155 (26), in PathBank - from 2 to 217 (31), in NCI - from 2 to 180 (20), in
151 Qiagen - from 2 to 709 (58), in Reactome - from 3 to 831 (36), Supplementary Figure S1.

152 Five source pathway datasets (Biocarta, KEGG, Qiagen, NCI, and Reactome) had only gene products
153 as the pathway nodes, and two datasets (PathBank and HumanCyc) also contained metabolites as the
154 interactors.

155 The percentage share of metabolic components per pathway was in the range of 0-94 (mean 74%) for
156 the pathways from Pathbank, and 6-95 (mean 70%) for the pathways from HumanCyc database.

157 All processed pathway datasets are available for download as both “.x/sx” files for each separate
158 pathway, and as combined “.csv” files for the whole dataset.

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160 **3.2. Pathway architecture**

161 In OncoboxPD, each molecular pathway is implemented as a graph of interactions between its
162 molecular participants. The graph edges are interactions between the nodes, such as protein-protein
163 interactions, biochemical reactions, transport to different cellular components, assembly or disruption
164 of molecular complexes, and other processes. Standard edge types in OncoboxPD are “activation”,
165 “inhibition” and “other” (Table 2). Each edge on the graph is directed, and when the underlying
166 interaction is reversible, then two oppositely directed edges are placed between the interactors.

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Table 2. Type of pathway graph edges in OncoboxPD

Initial edge type in Biopax or different format	Edge type in OncoboxPD format
Direct interaction, activation or inhibition	activation or inhibition, respectively
SubPathwayInteraction	other
ComplexAssembly	other
Molecular interaction (between participants from SubPathwayControl item) - activation or inhibition	activation or inhibition, respectively
Catalysis, activation or inhibition	activation or inhibition, respectively
Modulation (activation-allosteric, activation-nonallosteric, activation, inhibition-competitive, inhibition-other, inhibition-noncompetitive, inhibition-allosteric, inhibition-irreversible, inhibition)	activation or inhibition, respectively
Transport	activation, because it promotes further molecular interaction
BiochemicalReaction	activation, because it promotes further molecular interaction
Indirect	other
Compound	other
Others	other

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Graph vertexes (nodes) represent formal functional units of a pathway, or several molecular pathways that are interconnected on the graph (Table 3). Every node may include one or few components. For example, when a node stands for molecular complex, then it comprises few components which can be proteins (gene products) or non-protein molecules. In OncoboxPD, there is only one depth level for “molecular complex” nodes. Each node has an *activation/repressor role coefficient* (ARR) which characterizes its relation to the overall pathway physiological or molecular effect. ARR depends on role of an individual node is a pathway. In the current implementation, ARR=1 means that node is activator, ARR= -1 is for repressor, ARR=0 is for nodes with ambiguous or unclear function, and ARR=0.5 or ARR= -0.5 is for nodes with rather activator or rather repressor functions, respectively.

Table 3. Type and composition of pathway graph nodes in OncoboxPD.

Characteristic	Node type in OncoboxPD	Gene composition	Involvement in evaluation of ARR / PAL ^a	Example
Node with one or more gene products/components (proteins, nucleic acid molecules, small molecules,	participant	one or several gene products/components;	+/+ if node contains gene product	participant node <i>Ub</i> in HIF1Alpha pathway; gene products <i>UBB</i> , <i>UBC</i> , <i>UBD</i>

protein complexes, bound complexes)				
Node with name of biological effect, or with another crosslinking molecular pathway (entire pathway as single item)	participant	empty	+/-	participant node <i>Glycolysis</i> in 2-Ketoglutarate Dehydrogenase Complex Deficiency pathway
Auxiliary transport node	transport	empty	+/-	transport node <i>Ornithine</i> in Arginine and Proline Metabolism pathway. Citrulline transport from cytoplasm to mitochondrial matrix
Auxiliary biochemical reaction node	biochemical reaction	empty	+/-	reaction node <i>Glucose 1-phosphate + Uridine diphosphategalactose -> Galactose 1-phosphate + Uridine diphosphate glucose</i> in Congenital Disorder of Glycosylation CDG-IIa pathway

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^a “+” and “-” indicates involvement of node in evaluation of ARR coefficients or PAL values.

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ARR value of a node is translated into specific gene ARR, according to molecular functions that the respective gene product plays in all pathway nodes. This is mentioned because the same gene product can be involved in different nodes, sometimes with different ARRs. Thus, overall role of a gene product in a pathway must be weighted and characterized by an overall ARR value. This task can't be fulfilled effectively and unbiasedly by manual curation because of big number of pathways and their apparently high complexity. Thus, to uniformly annotate all pathways in OncoboxPD we used a recursive algorithm that was recently developed in our team to automatically annotate ARRs based on pathway graph architecture and connectivity [23].

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While a protein-protein interaction can be presented by an edge between two participants, biochemical reactions and transport processes require different format of graphic representation. Number of participants of biochemical reaction (input and output reactants, and enzymes) is typically more than two, and biochemical pathway most frequently cannot be shown as a sequential series of pairwise interactions. An auxiliary central node was introduced for biochemical reactions to link an enzyme with input and output reactants. Such central node denotes the process itself and has no components. Similar approach was used for transport processes to link input, output molecular participants, and a transporter. Thus, auxiliary central nodes enable presenting pathways as logical and uninterrupted scheme of molecular process.

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The direction of reactions could vary in the source pathway databases: “left to right”, “right to left”, “reversible”. We converted each reaction or interaction in the format “left to right”, and every reversible reaction was transformed into two coupled reactions.

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In OncoboxPD, each gene product is named according to HGNC nomenclature [27]. Full names of non-protein molecules were saved in the PathBank database format, *e.g.* “Adenosine triphosphate”. Additionally, molecular IDs are assigned, where possible, according to four different

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209 chemical databases: CAS [28], ChEBI [29], HMDB [30], PathWiz [31], and DrugBank [32]. If a
 210 molecule has no associated HGNC gene name, then it is not involved in calculation of pathway
 211 activation level (PAL) using gene expression data. However, such molecule may play a technically
 212 important role by connecting an overall pathway graph which is a prerequisite for algorithmic
 213 assignment of ARR.

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215 **3.3. Functional annotation of molecular pathways**

216 In OncoboxPD, an attempt was made to functionally characterize all pathways according to their
 217 molecular physiological implication. To this end, we used Gene Ontology (GO) annotations [33],
 218 and analyzed gene sets corresponding to molecular pathway components using *enrichGO* function
 219 of ClusterProfiler R package [34] to identify biological processes which are statistically significantly
 220 linked with each individual pathway. We then assigned these specific GO tags to the respective
 221 molecular pathways and functional groups of pathways were, therefore, formed as those having
 222 common GO tag(s) (Figure 1). Altogether, we identified 6 485 such functional groups (Figure 1).

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226 Figure 1. Schematic representation of molecular pathway functional classification according to GO
 227 terms enrichment. Each functional group corresponds to a specific GO term and includes pathways,
 228 where this GO term is statistically significantly enriched (adjusted p -value < 0.05). In this assay, only
 229 the pathways with unique gene compositions were considered.

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231 Different functional groups differed ~ three orders of magnitude by their representation and included
 232 1 - 1021 molecular pathways (Figure 2). The biggest functional groups with more than 800
 233 pathways are listed in Table 4.

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Table 4. Functional OncoboxPD pathway groups with more than 800 members.

Pathway functional group ID (GO Tag)	Number of pathways included
Activation of protein kinase activity	1021
Peptidyl-serine phosphorylation	937
Fc receptor signaling pathway	896
Response to peptide hormone	883
Regulation of MAP kinase activity	882
Immune response-activating cell surface receptor signaling pathway	869
Neuronal death	858
Regulation of neuron death	834
Positive regulation of cellular protein localization	833
Blood coagulation	817
Gland development	810
Positive regulation of cell adhesion	802

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Figure 2. Size distribution of GO functional groups of pathways (number of pathways included). Groups with more than 800 pathways are shown right to dashed red line.

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245 **3.4. Pathway activation level calculation**

246 *Pathway activation level (PAL)* is a metric allowing direct calculation of pathway activity levels using
247 high-throughput gene expression data *e.g.* obtained by transcriptomic or proteomic screens. It can take
248 positive and negative values in case of up- and downregulation of a pathway, respectively [1,7,35].
249 PAL values can serve to characterize molecular processes in-depth and in a large scale [19,35], or can
250 be used as the biomarkers for many aspects of human biology including molecular pathology and
251 personalized medicine [36–38]. In this version of OncoboxPD, we include PAL calculation and
252 visualization tool that can supplement the database with the functional analysis of the pathways.
253 OncoboxPD has Web-based built-in tool for PAL calculation that is available at
254 <https://open.oncobox.com>. User can upload expression data of interest to interrogate pathway
255 activation compared to controls. PALs are calculated according to [35] as follows:

$$256 \quad PAL_p = \sum_n ARR_{n,p} * \lg(CNR_n) / \sum_n |ARR_{n,p}| * 100,$$

257 where PAL_p is *PAL* for pathway p , CNR_n is *case-to-normal ratio*, ratio of gene n expression level in
258 a sample under study to average level in control group; *ARR* (see above; *activator/repressor role*) is
259 a Boolean value that depends on function of gene n product in pathway p . *ARR* can take values of
260 -1 when n inhibits p ; 1 when n activates p ; 0 when n has ambiguous or unknown role in p ; 0.5 and
261 -0.5 , when n is rather activator or inhibitor of p , respectively.

262 *PAL* calculator can use as the controls custom data provided by the user, or (default setting) human
263 tissue RNAseq profiles obtained from healthy donors killed in road accidents. User can upload file
264 with expression data and create a new analysis. At this stage, user can select pathway database, and
265 can use an auxiliary option “scores for control samples” that enables calculating *PAL* values for the
266 control samples to assess variations in the control group. The output results are returned as ready-to-
267 download tables with *CNR* and *PAL* values for all samples under analysis. Alternatively, the results
268 can be explored, analyzed and visualized with the web service. By clicking on the results, user can
269 obtain overall *PAL* table, Sample table and pathway activation chart for the group of samples under
270 analysis. Clicking on Sample table returns separate *PAL* datasheets for each sample. For every
271 pathway in a given sample, its pathway activation chart can be visualized by the software. The sample-
272 specific datasheet also includes *CNR* for all genes under analysis (for example, for up to 36183 genes
273 when profiles from the default collection are used as the norms), and $\log_2(CNR)$ values. In every
274 sample profile, each pathway ID can be clicked to obtain tabs for differentially expressed genes
275 included in this pathway and their *CNR*s; pathway nodes and components; static and dynamic pathway
276 graphic scheme.

277 Pathway activation chart is automatically generated for every sample or every group of samples
278 (Figure 3). It summarizes overall *PAL* calculation results and returns top 10 most strongly activated
279 pathways (ordered top to bottom) and top 10 most strongly inhibited pathways (ordered bottom to
280 top) with *PAL* values, their *p*-values and FDR-adjusted *p*-values (Benjamini – Hochberg correction).
281 The principle of *p*-value calculation is shown on Table 5.

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Figure 3. Example of pathway activation chart. Green lines show top 10 most strongly activated pathways (ordered top to bottom), red lines show top 10 most strongly inhibited pathways (ordered bottom to top). Thickness is proportionate to absolute value of PAL. In this example, RNA sequencing gene expression profiles of 51 papillary thyroid cancer samples [39] were compared with six healthy thyroid normal samples from ANTE collection [40]. PAL values, t-test *p*-values and FDR-adjusted *p*-values are shown right to the pathway names.

Table 5. Principle of *p*-value calculation for pathway activation chart.

Number of control samples	Number of case samples (replicates) under analysis	Method of <i>p</i> -value calculation
3 or more	3 or more	t -test
3 or more	1	<i>p</i> -value is defined as a quantile of PAL in a sample investigated relatively to PAL distribution in control samples
less than 3	any number	<i>p</i> -value is not calculated

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Pathway activation chart represents top most strongly activated and most strongly inhibited molecular pathways in a sample/group of samples. The number of displayed top pathways can be selected by the user. When a group of samples is investigated, then t-test *p*-value is shown for the comparison between case and control groups. All graphic materials generated are available for download as .png and .svg files. The detailed guidelines for PAL calculation and analysis with step-by-step screenshots is available through open.oncobox.com. Also, three thyroid cancer expression

302 profiles are preloaded for each user as demo example of samples with PAL calculating results (using
 303 six healthy thyroid samples from ANTE collection as control group).
 304 Alternatively, we also developed a Python library *oncoboxlib*, that can be run on local computer and
 305 can be freely downloaded by the user. To calculate PAL values, *Oncoboxlib* requires files with
 306 HGNC gene symbols [27] and the corresponding expression levels for at least one case and at least
 307 one control sample. Installation instruction for *Oncoboxlib* and demo-example are available in
 308 Supplementary File 1 and at <https://pypi.org/project/oncoboxlib>.

309 3.5. Pathway visualization.

310 OncoboxPD collection is supplemented by pathway visualization tool. It allows to interactively
 311 visualize pathway structure and internal molecular interactions in the format of static or dynamic
 312 directed graph (Figure 4 A, B).
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315 Figure 4. TRAF molecular pathway visualization using OncoboxPD software. Nodes correspond to
316 individual pathway components or to their complexes. Color of every node reflects logarithm of
317 mean CNR for all node components, according to a scale given with green upregulated, and red
318 downregulated nodes. Grey nodes have no gene components, and no CNR values. Nodes that are
319 unaffected (with $CNR \sim 1$) are shown white. Red and green arrows stand for inhibitory and activating
320 interactions, respectively. Ovals denote gene products, octagons - metabolites, hexagons –
321 complexes, and other nodes (text labels without recognized molecular components) are shown as
322 rectangles. In this example, RNA sequencing gene expression profile of thyroid papillary cancer
323 sample TC-53 [39] was compared against six healthy thyroid samples from ANTE collection [40].
324 A) Static pathway graph. B) Projection of dynamic interactive pathway graph. The figure can be
325 found following the path: result file in Folders(“example” with green icon)->sample TC53 in
326 Sample table-> Pathway activation level tab->TRAF Pathway-> static and dynamic graphs.

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328 Therein, static graph automatically obtains optimal layout to avoid node or line overlap and to adapt
329 node size to its labels (Figure 4A). As an option, user can switch from optimal to compact layer mode
330 to decrease distances between the nodes. In turn, dynamic graph is interactive scheme that can be
331 moved using Cytoscape plugin, where user can customize the layer by dragging the items (nodes)
332 with mouse. This option is helpful in case of complicated interactions and long node labels.

333 Color of each node reflects logarithm of mean CNR for all of its components and corresponds to a
334 scale given below with green color for upregulated, and red color for downregulated nodes. The
335 default scale is designed to represent all $\lg(CNR)$ variabilities present on the graph for the case under
336 investigation. However, user can customize color intensity by manually selecting scale limits, but this
337 can lead to equal maximum color intensity for some nodes if they exceed the scale threshold. Such
338 nodes will be marked by bold black frame. The nodes shown by grey color have no gene components
339 and no CNR values. Unaffected or poorly affected nodes (with $CNR \sim 1$, and $\lg(CNR) \sim 0$) are shown
340 white.

341 Red arrows show inhibitory interactions, green arrows - activating interactions; arrows for ambiguous
342 or poorly investigated interactions are shown black. Arrows involved in biochemical reactions or
343 transport processes are comprised as the activating interactions. Auxiliary central nodes of
344 biochemical reactions and transport processes have rhombic shape and are filled in black with no label
345 because they denote the process but not its molecular participants (Figure 5). Such nodes without gene
346 products involved have no CNR values, but they are necessary for ARR assignment to all pathway
347 graph members.

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351 Figure 5. OncoboxPD visualization of *De novo triacylglycerol biosynthesis* molecular pathway.
352 Nodes correspond to pathway participants or their complexes. Color reflects node activation according
353 to color scale on the bottom. For this example, thyroid papillary cancer sample TC-53 RNA
354 sequencing profile [39] was normalized on six healthy thyroid samples from ANTE collection [40].
355 Nodes that don't correspond to known gene products are shown grey because for them no CNR value
356 can be calculated. Auxiliary central nodes of biochemical reactions (BR) have rhombic shape and are
357 filled in black. Ovals denote gene products, octagons - metabolites, hexagons – complexes, and other
358 nodes (text labels without recognized molecular components) are shown as rectangles. Green arrows
359 denote activating interactions. The figure can be found following the path: result file in Folders
360 ("example" with green icon) ->sample TC53 in Sample table-> Pathway activation level tab-> De
361 novo triacylglycerol biosynthesis pathway -> static graph.

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364 **3.6.Human interactome graph of protein interactions and metabolic reactions**

365 Using collection of pathways as the knowledgebase of molecular interactions, we also built combined
366 human interactome and metabolome model. This is the directed graph, where nodes are genes or
367 metabolites, and edges are known pairwise molecular interactions present in the OncoboxPD. The
368 model was visualized using Gephi software and ForceAtlas2 algorithm [41] (Figure 6).
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372 Figure 6. Human interactome model of protein interactions and metabolic reactions. Graph vertices
 373 represent pathway participants: gene products (green), metabolites (blue) and auxiliary nodes/nodes
 374 with label of biological effect (grey). Graph edges are interactions between pathway participants.
 375 Edges inherit color from donor nodes.

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377 Totally, we used molecular architectures of 50 178 different pathways. Complex pathway nodes
 378 containing n molecular participants were divided into n nodes with only one participant. Thus, each
 379 vertex represents one pathway participant on the graph. We then combined all pathway graphs
 380 together based on the coinciding gene products and metabolites. The resulting interactome graph
 381 includes 122 929 vertices and 600 137 edges. It incorporates totally 64 095 molecular participants
 382 and 361 654 interactions (excluding auxiliary nodes and interactions).

383 From all these pathways, we excluded molecular participants which were not connected within the
384 overall network (less than 1% of the initial pathway members). The remaining molecular interactors
385 formed a connected graph. The graph density was 8.08×10^{-5} , average vertex degree (the number of
386 edges connecting the vertex) was 4.9. However, some vertices had extremely high vertex degree, for
387 example, 25 336 for Cytidine monophosphate, 24 034 for Coenzyme A, 23 300 for gene product
388 *CRLS1*, 22 718 for gene product *DGATI*, 2 813 for gene product *PEMT*, and 2 799 for S-
389 Adenosylmethionine. The interactome model built enables finding the shortest path between genes
390 of interest, or to identify gene interactomic neighborhood (e.g. at the distance of one, two or three
391 edges). The model built is available in *graphml* format (10.6084/m9.figshare.16617676.)

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393 4. Discussion

394 We report here OncoboxPD collection that includes 51 672 molecular pathways, which is to our
395 knowledge currently the biggest human molecular pathways database with functionally
396 characterized individual pathway nodes. Furthermore, all pathways are functionally classified
397 according to GO terms enrichment patterns. OncoboxPD is a structured curated collection of
398 protein-based and of metabolic human molecular pathways. All pathway participants, their
399 interactions and reactions are uniformly processed and annotated, and are ready for numeric analysis
400 of experimental expression data.

401 There are several previously published knowledge bases that systematically aggregate information
402 related to molecular pathways. For example, OmniPath accumulates data in the form of five databases
403 including annotations of signaling network interactions, enzyme-post-translational modification
404 relationships, characteristics of individual proteins, protein complexes, and of their roles in
405 intercellular communication [42]. OmniPath has web-based, R, Cytoscape, and python applications
406 which can generate and visualize custom (e.g. tissue specific) molecular networks and calculate
407 specific enrichment scores for them. However, there is no option of calculating functional molecular
408 pathway activation metrics using gene/protein expression data.

409 In turn, Scalable Precision Medicine Open Knowledge Engine (SPOKE) resource aggregates several
410 relevant databases of not only molecular pathways, but also of diseases, symptoms, biological
411 processes, genes and their products [43]. It can generate and visualize molecular networks based on
412 the built-in databases. However, the source datasets cannot be extracted by the user.

413 In ConsensusPathDB database, individual molecular interactions are catalogued, and user can
414 interrogate enrichment of specific gene networks [44]. However, no molecular pathway information
415 can be found and extracted.

416 The Pathway Commons tool combines many pathways-related databases, and has R, Cytoscape, and
417 Java packages enabling to visualize and to certain extent to analyze the pathways [45]. On the other
418 hand, it cannot calculate pathway activation metrics, and has no option of building pathway activation
419 charts.

420 We conclude, therefore, that OncoboxPD has the following advantages:

- 421 -presenting molecular pathways in a uniform format that is ready for directly functionally assessing
422 pathway activation metrics;
- 423 -built-in tool for calculating pathway activation levels (PALs) for 50K+ molecular pathways using
424 custom RNA/protein expression data;
- 425 -quick graph overview of most strongly differentially regulated pathways;
- 426 -visualization of pathway activation charts in two alternative (static and dynamic) modes, where color
427 of each node of a given pathway reflects its up/downregulation in a sample of interest;
- 428 -both the results of analysis and source databases are free to download.

429 We did not aggregate here neither databases which may contain data with remarkably different levels
430 of evidence like WikiPathways that can be edited by the users, nor datasets of pairwise molecular

431 interactions (like IntAct). Unfortunately, we couldn't quantitatively estimate the reliability of each
432 piece of data included in OncoboxPD because pathway construction was done by expert teams
433 managing the source databases using different approaches, datasets, and algorithms. However, we can
434 highlight some technical limitations of data presentation and storage which are peculiar to certain
435 source knowledgebases. First, using of non-machine-readable formats may lead to loss of certain
436 information. For example, KEGG database uses graphical .png format and original xml-based KGML
437 format, and ceased to support universal BioPAX format. In KEGG, graphical format frequently
438 contains information that is not included in machine-readable KGML format, e.g. biological process
439 names, conditions of interactions, labels of spatial compartments, or separately given participants
440 without clear links to other interactors.

441 In turn, PathBank database provides several alternative formats for each pathway: BioPAX, SBGN,
442 SBML, PWML, RXN, and SDF. But only one of them, i.e. PWML (PathBank original format),
443 contains all the information from the corresponding visual map. However, even there some elements
444 may have only coordinates for the picture, but no information about their link with other process
445 participants. Such labels are absent in other formats, thus leading to partial loss of data.

446 Furthermore, the universal format BioPAX has no clear direction and type of interaction in
447 "subpathway" items in several cases, when interactors are simultaneously "activators" and "activated"
448 or "inhibitors" and "inhibited" without a clear link between certain role and certain interaction or
449 reaction. Qiagen SABiosciences database provided data only in the graphic format that had to be
450 manually curated during construction of OncoboxPD. Another important issue is maintenance of the
451 above source databases, their regular updates and availability. For example, the databases Biocarta
452 and NCI PID ceased to exist in their original form, but were saved in various aggregator resources
453 after specific data processing, that theoretically could alter data completeness

454 In the examples given, we explained PAL calculation for RNA expression data. However, the same
455 algorithms may be also applied for the quantitative proteomic profiles. In addition, algorithmic
456 assessment of pathway mutation enrichment, e.g. in cancer samples [46–48], will be another
457 possible direction of developing this database. The current pathway activity assessment interface is
458 tailored to analyze gene expression/proteomic data, but further updates may increase its functionality
459 to assess also high-throughput metabolomic profiles. Another direction of future investigations is
460 cross-linking gene/protein expression profiles with metabolomic data for the hybrid pathways
461 including both gene products and metabolites, as shown on Figure 5. Such integration requires
462 differential weighting of the PAL values obtained after gene/protein expression data and
463 metabolomic profiles, which is currently unsolved problem and will be a matter of further studies.

464 Five out of seven source databases of OncoboxPD collection contain only protein-protein
465 interactions (Table 1), and two remaining datasets contain also metabolite interaction data. To our
466 knowledge, there is still no analytic system for pathway-level processing of high-throughput
467 metabolomic data, and this may be important direction of future OncoboxPD development. For
468 example, quantitative metabolomic data could be employed to calculate activation levels for the
469 metabolic pathways, where the case-to-normal ratios (CNRs) will be found by comparing metabolite
470 concentrations in the case and control biosamples.

471 In the future, we plan to maintain OncoboxPD a growing database that will be regularly updated
472 when new pathways, or their more relevant functional annotations become available.

473 In OncoboxPD, we for the first time uniformly algorithmically classified large collection of molecular
474 pathways according to the physiological processes they are involved by using Gene Ontology terms.
475 The same approach may be employed for annotating new pathway collections, and such functional
476 labels may be important to identify groups of relevant processes specific to certain conditions. For
477 example, it was shown recently that signaling, cytoskeleton, metabolic and DNA repair pathways have
478 distinct features in mutation accumulation and transcriptional activation in cancer [19].

479 Finally, OncoboxPD is currently the collection of human pathways and related analytic tools, whereas
480 in the future it can be expanded to a number of model organisms where large-scale interactomic data
481 are available.

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484 **Availability of data and materials**

485 OncoboxPD database and the corresponding built-in tools are freely available at
486 <https://open.oncobox.com>. OncoboxPD can be accessed in two ways: by starting a new session (no
487 registration needed), or by continuing previous session (authorization required). More detailed
488 description of the access modes is given in the Help section at open.oncobox.com. The option of PAL
489 calculation is also possible using *oncoboxlib* Python library, available at
490 <https://gitlab.com/oncobox/oncoboxlib>.

491

492 **Author contributions**

493 MSo, MZ, VE, NB collected and processed molecular data. MSo, AB, MR, DK curated pathway data.
494 AS, NB, VT performed tool development. AGu and MZ functionally classified pathways. MZ, MSo,
495 VE, VT did statistical calculations. MSe, AGa, VT, DK, and AB planned and supervised the research
496 and relevant infrastructure development. AB and MZ wrote the paper.

497

498 **Conflicts of interest:**

499 MZ, VT, AGa, AGu, MSo have a financial relationship with Omicsway Corp. The remaining authors
500 declare that they have no conflict of interest.

501

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652 **Supplementary material legends:**

653 Supplementary Figure S1. Distribution of pathway size (number of participants in a pathway) for
654 seven pathway subsets.

655 Supplementary File 1. Guidelines for python package *oncoboxlib*.

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